

New and efficient methodology of aldehyde synthesis from alkyl halide using α -chloro nitron as a new, stable and potential oxidizing reagent

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Abstract : Consecutive S_N2 reaction of α -chloro nitrones are studied with alkyl halides and the nitrones are found to have remarkable oxidizing properties for the conversion of alkyl halides to aldehydes with high yield. In addition, the side product obtained can serve as efficient dipolarophile in 1,3-DCR to produce spiro cycloadducts in good yields.

Keywords : α -Chloro nitron, S_N2 reaction, aldehyde synthesis, spiro cycloadduct.

Introduction

Conversion of alkyl halides to aldehydes using *N*-oxide with moderate yields have been already reported (Krohnke reaction). In addition to the existing methods available for the synthesis of aldehyde from alkyl halides¹⁻⁶, we would like to incorporate an efficient one pot synthesis of aldehyde from alkyl halides using for the

first time α -chloro nitrones (**1**) as a new, stable and potential oxidizing reagent with an excellent yield (Scheme 1, Table 1). In addition, the side product (furan derivatives, **2**) obtained during aldehyde synthesis has been successfully used as dipolarophile in 1,3-DCR with nitron (**1**) for the production of spiro cycloadducts (**3**) with high yields (almost 75–85%; Scheme 2). α -Chloro

Reagents and conditions : (i) Dry ether, pyridine, room temperature, N_2 atmosphere

(ii) Dry ether, Na_2CO_3 , room temperature, N_2 atmosphere

Scheme 1

Table 1. Aldehyde synthesis using α -chloro nitrones

Entry	Nitronone	Alkyl halide ^a	Product ^b	Time (h)	Yield ^c (%)
1	R = Me	Benzyl chloride	Benzaldehyde	5	88
2	R = Me	1-Chloro propane	Propionaldehyde	6	87
3	R = Ph	Benzyl chloride	Benzaldehyde	5	88
4	R = Ph	<i>n</i> -Butyl chloride	<i>n</i> -Butyraldehyde	6	86
5	R = Me	<i>p</i> -Hydroxy benzyl chloride	<i>p</i> -Hydroxy benzaldehyde	4	89
6	R = Ph	<i>p</i> -Hydroxy benzyl chloride	<i>p</i> -Hydroxy benzaldehyde	5	89

^aReaction condition : α -Chloro nitronone (3.0198 mmol), alkyl halide (1 equivalent), dry ether, Py, Na_2CO_3 , N_2 atmosphere, room temperature.

^bAll the compounds were characterized by IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, MS, HRMS spectral data.

^cIsolated yield after purification.

nitrones (**1**) are more reactive than other nitrones due to the electron withdrawing effect of chlorine and therefore can act as more powerful oxidizing agent than other nitrones.

Literature survey reveals that aldehyde synthesis using nitronone as active oxidizing reagent and further use of side products (obtained during aldehyde synthesis) as dipolarophile in cycloaddition reactions are not yet known and hence can be incorporated as an important application in nitronone chemistry. Synthesis and 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of *N*-phenyl- α -chloro nitronone^{7,8} (**1**, R = Ph) has been already reported. Following the same methodology and the methodology suggested by Eschenmoser *et al.*⁹, novel *N*-methyl- α -chloro nitronone (**1**,

R = Me) has been synthesized as white crystalline solid, m.p. 52 °C (uncorrected) and used for aldehyde synthesis as oxidizing reagent.

Results and discussion

α -Chloro nitrones (**1**) are moderately stable and can be isolated while transient nitronone **1a** can not be isolated because of its high instability and undergoes decomposition at room temperature. The lone pair of electron of the OH group of α -chloro nitronone facilitates intramolecular $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ reaction in presence of pyridine and is actually the driving force for the development of transient nitronone **1a**. Nitronone **1a** reacts very quickly with different alkyl halides ($\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ reaction) and develops an intermediate compound **1b**. The labile N-O bond of **1b** undergoes clea-

Reaction condition : (i) Dry ether, room temperature, N_2 atmosphere, 5–8 h.

Scheme 2

vage¹⁰ when the reaction mixture is stirred with solid sodium carbonate which plays an important role for the development of aldehyde and furan derivative (2) as side product in a Kornblum type process (Scheme 1; Table 1). The novelty of the study is the use of α -chloro nitrene as an oxidizing reagent in aldehyde synthesis and newly developed side product as dipolarophile in cycloaddition reactions. The isolated side products (2) are equally efficient like other conventional dipolarophiles used for cycloaddition reactions and leads to the formation of regioselective 5-substituted spiro cycloadducts (3)^{11,12} in 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction with nitrene 1 (Scheme 2) and thereby offering greater scope for its applications. The yield of the isolated aldehydes are extremely high in a much lesser time (85–89%) and are much better in case of active alkyl halides compared to inactive alkyl halides. The results are summarized in Table 1. The beauty of the reaction lies in addition of pyridine at the beginning to generate transient nitrene (1a) which is only capable of developing furan derivative (2) as side product and can be utilized as a new efficient dipolarophile in 1,3-DCR and thereby the reaction as a whole becomes atom efficient. Simple nitrenes¹³ (benzaldehyde derived nitrene) can also be employed as an oxidizing reagent for aldehyde synthesis (synthesized *n*-butyraldehyde : yield 78%) but the side product obtained is a waste and can not be used for further reactions. At the outset of this work it was not clear about the development of transient nitrene (1a) but after completion of the study and spectral analysis of side product (2), the development of transient nitrene 1a was confirmed. The products especially aldehydes are known compounds and spectral data of the synthesized aldehydes are almost identical to the values found in literature. For example, sharp singlet signals at δ 9.80 and 198.00 in the NMR spectrum (¹H, ¹³C respectively) along with molecular ion peak at 106, base peak at 105 and peaks at 77, 51 in the mass spectrum give strong evidence in favour of benzaldehyde formation. The oxidation side product (2) was obtained as single isomer having *E* configuration in all the cases and the yield of the side product was almost 10–13% when isolated in pure condition. The spectral data of the oxidation side products (2) also agreed well with the assigned structures. The spiro cycloadducts (3) were obtained as regioselective

single isomer predominantly in 1,3-DCR of α -chloro nitrene (1) with side product (2) having high yields (70–85%) when isolated in pure condition. The stereochemistry of the 5-substituted regioselective spiro cycloadducts (3) in all the cases were rationalized by considering the multiplicity of the proton signals at 3-H, 4-H and CHCl asymmetric centres along with their coupling constant values^{14,15}. In the spiro isoxazolidine derivatives (3), 3-H resonates around δ_H 3.50 to 2.50 ppm while for the 4-H around δ_H 5.80 to 3.00 ppm and the coupling constant is $J_{3,4} \sim 9.20$ Hz implying a *cis* relationship between H-3 and H-4. The CHCl proton also resonates around δ_H 2.60 to 2.20 ppm. The 3-H and CHCl protons are also *syn* as evident from their coupling constant values ($J_{3,CHCl} \sim 9.16$ to 9.40 Hz)^{14,15}. Cycloaddition of Z nitrene (both the reported α -chloro nitrenes are of Z configuration in this communication) via *exo* transition state geometry results in the formation of *syn* isoxazolidine derivatives. Cycloaddition reaction using furan derivatives (2) with other simple nitrenes^{13,16,17} are in progress using the same methodology. A preferential conformation for the spiro regioselective isoxazolidine derivatives (3) may be represented in Fig. 1. Reaction of nitrene 1 with methyl iodide and ethyl bromide was also studied for the synthesis of formaldehyde and acetaldehyde respectively but no significant results were obtained because of the volatility of formaldehyde and difficulties associated with the synthesis of acetaldehyde. These are the drawbacks of this methodology.

Fig. 1. General conformation for the cycloadducts 3.

Experimental

¹H NMR spectra were recorded with a Bruker Avance DPX 400 spectrometer (400 MHz, FT NMR) using TMS as internal standard. ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on the same instrument at 100 MHz. The coupling constants

(*J*) are given in Hz. IR spectra were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer RX 1-881 machine as film or KBr pellets for all the products. Mass spectra were recorded with a Jeol SX-102 (FAB) instrument. The HRMS spectra were recorded on a Q-ToF micro instrument (YA-105). TLC was carried out on Fluka silica gel TLC cards while column chromatography was performed with silica gel (E. Merck, India) 60–200 mesh. All other reagents and solvents were purified after receiving from commercial suppliers. *N*-Methylhydroxylamine was purchased from Aldrich Chemical Company and was used as received. *N*-Phenylhydroxylamine was prepared following standard methods available in literature and has been used in synthesis¹⁸⁻²⁰.

General procedure for the synthesis of nitrone 1 (R = Me) :

N-Methylhydroxylamine (250 mg, 5.3127 mmol) was added to chlorohydrin (720 mg, 1 equivalent) in dry ether (50 ml) and anhydrous MgSO₄. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature with constant stirring with a magnetic stirrer under N₂ atmosphere for 10 h. The formation of nitrone was monitored by TLC (*R_f* = 0.34). The nitrone was isolated under reduced pressure vacuum pump as white niddle shape crystals (920 mg, 94%; m.p. 52 °C, uncorrected).

Spectroscopic data for nitrone 1 (R = Me) :

Yield : 920 mg (94%); white niddle shape crystals; *R_f* = 0.43, m.p. 52 °C (uncorrected); IR (KBr) : 3595–3470 (br), 1660 (s), 1610 (s), 1415 (m), 1185 (s) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 5.84 (1H, d, CH=N⁺), 5.79 (1H, br, -OH, exchanged in D₂O), 3.51 (1H, dt, *J* 6.16, 6.08 Hz, CHCl), 3.31 (3H, s, N⁺-CH₃), 1.88–1.15 (6H, m, CH₂ protons); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 141.55 (CH=N⁺), 55.76 (CHCl), 34.84 (N⁺-CH₃), 28.50, 27.22, 26.00 (3CH₂ carbons); HRMS-EI : Calcd. for C₆H₁₂O₂NCl, (M), 165.5710, Found : M⁺, 165.5698.

General procedure for synthesis of aldehyde (benzaldehyde) and furan derivative 2 (entry 1; Table 1) :

To a stirred solution of nitrone 1 (R = Me; 500 mg, 3.0198 mmol) in dry ether (25 ml) pyridine (1 equivalent) was added and stirred at room temperature with a magnetic stirrer under N₂ atmosphere for 1 h while the formation of transient nitrone 1a (not isolated) was monitored by TLC (*R_f* = 0.38). Benzyl chloride (292.1002

mg, 1 equivalent) was added at this stage and the reaction mixture was stirred for another 3 h till the intermediate compound 1b (not isolated) was developed (monitored by TLC; *R_f* = 0.40). 2 g of solid Na₂CO₃ was added at this stage and the reaction mixture was stirred for further 1 h while the progress of the reaction was again monitored by TLC (*R_f* = 0.43, 0.50). The reaction was typically completed when the N–O bond was cleaved. Basic workup, removal of pyridine hydrochloride and silica gel column chromatographic purification using ethyl acetate-hexane provided desired benzaldehyde as colourless liquid (712 mg, 89% ; *R_f* = 0.43) and furan derivative (2) as pale yellow gummy liquid (88 mg, 10% ; *R_f* = 0.50). This procedure was followed for all the substrates listed in Table 1.

Spectroscopic data for benzaldehyde (entry 1) :

Yield : 712 mg (88%); colourless liquid; *R_f* = 0.43; IR (KBr) : 1695 (s), 1320 (m), 770 (s) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 9.80 (1H, s, CHO), 7.30–7.16 (5H, m, C₆H₅); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 198.00 (CHO), 136.20, 134.55, 132.60, 131.00 (aromatic carbons); FAB-MS (*m/z*) : 106 (M⁺), 105 (B.P), 77, 51, 28; HRMS-EI : Calcd. for C₆H₅CHO (M), 106.0417, Found : M⁺, 106.0408.

Spectroscopic data for 2 (R=Me; α-N-methyl furan derivative; entry 1) [(E)-1-(dihydrofuran-2-(3H)-ylidene)-N-methyl methanamine] :

Yield : 88 mg (10%); pale yellow gummy liquid; *R_f* = 0.50; IR (KBr) : 3125–3054 (br), 2838 (m), 1652 (s), 1455 (m), 1210 (m) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 4.81 (1H, br, N–H), 4.56 (1H, s, C=CH), 3.30 (N–Me), 2.50–2.16 (6H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 103.00, 101.76 (double bonded carbons), 26.22, 25.30, 23.65 (3CH₂ carbons); FAB-MS (*m/z*) : 113 (M⁺), 98, 97; HRMS-EI : Calcd. for C₆H₁₁ON (M), 113.1000, Found : M⁺, 112.9876.

Spectroscopic data for propionaldehyde (entry 2) :

Yield : 592 mg (87%); colourless liquid; *R_f* = 0.50; IR (KBr) : 2920 (m), 2720 (m), 1720 (s) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 9.70 (1H, t, *J* 6.60 Hz, -CHO), 2.30 (2H, ddd, *J* 6.08, 6 Hz, -CH₂), 1.00 (3H, t, *J* 6.30 Hz, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 202.40 (CHO), 44.22 (CH₂ carbon), 35.55 (CH₃ carbon); FAB-MS (*m/z*) : 58 (M⁺), 57, 29 (B.P); HRMS-EI : Calcd. for C₃H₆O (M), 58.0417, Found : M⁺, 58.0403.

Spectroscopic data for 2 (*R*=Ph; α -*N*-phenyl furan derivative; entry 4) [(*E*)-1-(dihydrofuran-2-(3*H*)-ylidene)-*N*-phenyl methanamine] :

Yield : 90 mg (11.5%); dark yellow viscous liquid; R_f = 0.46; IR (KBr) : 3150–3060 (br), 2860 (m), 1640 (s), 1430 (m), 1140 (m), 778 (s) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 7.83 (5H, m, C_6H_5), 6.24 (1H, br, N-H), 2.17 (1H, s, C=CH), 1.79–1.18 (6H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 137.20, 135.65, 134.00, 132.15 (aromatic carbons), 106.24, 104.18 (double bonded carbons), 28.46, 27.10, 24.84 (3CH_2 carbons). FAB-MS (m/z) : 175 (M^+), 98, 97, 77; HRMS-EI : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{ON}$ (M), 175.0993, Found : M^+ , 175.0981.

Spectroscopic data for *n*-butyraldehyde (entry 4) :

Yield : 570 mg (86%); colourless liquid; R_f = 0.54; IR (KBr) : 2945 (m), 2710 (m), 1730 (s) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 9.30 (1H, t, J 5.84 Hz, -CHO), 3.50 (2H, dt, J 6.50, 4.22 Hz, $-\text{C}_2\text{H}$), 1.30 (2H, ddd, J 5.50, 3.40 Hz, C_3H), 0.90 (3H, t, J 4.30 Hz, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 208.20 (CHO), 47.50 (C_2 carbon), 36.10 (C_3 carbon), 20.10 (C_4 carbon); FAB-MS (m/z) : 72 (M^+), 71, 57, 44 (B.P), 29; HRMS-EI : Calcd. for $\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}$ (M), 72.0670, Found : M^+ , 72.0523.

Spectroscopic data for *p*-hydroxy benzaldehyde (entry 5) :

Yield : 776 mg (89%); colourless liquid; R_f = 0.40; IR (KBr) : 1690 (s), 1320 (m), 1210 (m), 782 (s) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 9.76 (1H, s, CHO), 7.05–6.93 (4H, m, C_6H_5), 5.80 (1H, s, OH); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 201.64 (CHO), 134.10, 132.74, 130.40, 128.50 (aromatic carbons); FAB-MS (m/z) : 122 (M^+), 93, 92 (B.P), 29; HRMS-EI : Calcd. for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2$ (M), 122.0530, Found : M^+ , 122.0512.

General procedure for cycloaddition reaction of nitrone 1 (*R* = Ph) with furan derivative 2 (*R* = Ph) :

To a stirred solution of *N*-phenyl- α -chloro nitrone 1 (*R* = Ph; 61.8375 mg, 0.2855 mmol) in 25 ml dry ether was added 2 (*R* = Ph, 50 mg, 0.2855 mmol, 1 equivalent) and stirred at room temperature with a magnetic stirrer under N_2 atmosphere for 5 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC (R_f = 0.46). After completion of the reaction, the solvent was evaporated using a rotary evaporator to afford crude cycloadduct 3 (*R* = Ph) which was purified by column chromatography using ethyl acetate-hexane and was obtained as dark red viscous liq-

uid 3 (*R* = Ph; 95 mg, 85% ; Scheme 2). This procedure was followed for the synthesis of other spiro cycloadducts 3 (*R* = Me).

3 (*R* = Ph)

(*S*)-4-Chloro-4-((3*S*,4*S*,5*R*)-2-phenyl-4-(phenylamino)-1,6-dioxa-2-azaspiro[4.4]nonan-3-yl)butan-1-ol :

Spectroscopic data for 3 (*R* = Ph) :

Yield : 95 mg (85%); dark red viscous liquid; R_f = 0.46; IR (CHCl_3) : 3485–3290 (br), 2825 (m), 2425 (m), 1620 (s), 1445 (m), 1260 (m), 1040 (m), 780 (s) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 6.98–6.93 (10H, m, $2 \times \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$), 5.84 (1H, d, J 9.20 Hz, C_4H), 4.96 (1H, br, CH_2OH , exchanged in D_2O), 3.51 (1H, dd, J 9.34, 7.88 Hz, C_3H), 3.45 (1H, s, N-H proton), 2.61 (1H, dt, J 9.44, 8.72 Hz, CHCl), 1.88–1.15 (12H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 138.00, 136.50, 134.30, 133.80, 131.75, 130.42, 129.46, 128.64 (aromatic carbons), 95.10 (CHCl), 86.40 (C_5), 73.75 (C_3), 53.30 (C_4), 30.20, 28.55, 27.34, 26.22, 25.73, 24.37 (6CH_2 carbons); MS (m/z) : 404 ($\text{M}^+ + 2$), 402 (M^+), 325, 310, 309, 218 (B.P), 107, 91, 77; HRMS-EI : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ (M), 402.7130, Found : M^+ , 402.7122.

3 (*R* = Me)

(*S*)-4-Chloro-4-((3*S*,4*S*,5*R*)-2-methyl-4-(methylamino)-1,6-dioxa-2-azaspiro[4.4]nonan-3-yl)butan-1-ol :

Spectroscopic data for 3 (*R* = Me) :

Yield : 91 mg (83%); red gummy liquid; R_f = 0.40; IR (CHCl_3) : 3460–3326 (br), 2835 (m), 2420 (m), 1440 (m), 1325 (m), 980 (m) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 4.83 (1H, br, CH_2OH , exchanged in D_2O), 4.50 (1H, br, NHCH_3), 3.31 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 2.99 (1H, d, J 9.16

Hz, C₄H), 2.50 (1H, dd, *J* 9.06, 7.60 Hz, C₃H), 2.19 (1H, dt, *J* 9.16, 8.50 Hz, CHCl), 1.66–1.60 (12H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃): δ 93.00 (CHCl), 87.55 (C₃), 76.20 (C₃), 55.20 (C₄), 41.97 (N-CH₃), 40.24 (NH-CH₃), 33.37, 31.50, 28.68, 26.00, 25.12, 23.40 (6CH₂ carbons); MS (*m/z*): 280 (M⁺+2), 278 (M⁺), 263, 248, 156 (B.P), 141, 107; HRMS-EI: Calcd. for C₁₂H₂₃O₃N₂Cl (M), 278.6710, Found: M⁺, 278.6698.

Conclusion :

Finally, we developed a new atom efficient methodology for the aldehyde synthesis using α-chloro nitronne as oxidizing reagent and considered further reaction carried out on the side product with α-chloro nitronnes in 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction for the development of stereochemically important 5-spiro isoxazolidines. The formation of the desired cycloadducts were obtained in good yields within a short reaction time. The newly developed side products (furan derivatives, 2) are equally effective as dipolarophile in cycloaddition reactions like other conventional dipolarophiles used for cycloaddition reactions. The notable advantages offered by this method are one pot synthesis, simple operation, easy workup, mild and faster reaction conditions with high yield of products.

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References

1. V. Bertini, F. Lucchesini, M. Pocci and S. Alfei, *Tetrahedron*, 2005, 61, 9519.

2. J. Tang, J. Zhu, Z. Shen and Y. Zhang, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2007, 48, 1919.
 3. A. R. Katritzky, M. J. Cook, S. B. Brown, R. Cruz, G. H. Millet and A. Anani, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1979, 2493.
 4. G. Cardillo, M. Orena and S. Sandri, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1976, 190.
 5. S. V. Lieberman, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 77, 1114.
 6. W. P. Griffith, J. M. Jolliffe, S. V. Ley, P. D. Tiffin and K. F. Springhorn, *Synth. Commun.*, 1992, 22, 237.
 7. B. Chakraborty, S. Kafley and M. S. Chhetri, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2009, 48, 447.
 8. B. Chakraborty, S. Kafley, M. S. Chhetri and A. Samanta, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2010, 49, 209.
 9. U. M. Kempe, T. K. Dasgupta, K. Blatt, P. Gygax and A. Eschenmoser, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1972, 55, 2187.
 10. W. R. Hoffmann, G. Eichler and A. Endesfelder, *Liebigs. Ann. Chem.*, 1983, 2000.
 11. R. Newton and P. G. Savage, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 2008, 61, 432 and references cited therein.
 12. K. Aouadik, S. Vidal and P. J. Praly, *Synlett.*, 2006, 19, 3299 and references cited therein.
 13. V. K. Aggarwal, R. S. Grainger, H. Adams and P. L. Spargo, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1998, 63, 3481 and references cited therein.
 14. P. Deshong, W. Li, J. W. Kennington and H. L. Ammon, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1991, 56, 1364.
 15. B. Chakraborty, P. Sharma, N. Rai, S. Kafley and M. S. Chhetri, *J. Chem. Res.*, 2010, 3, 147.
 16. B. Chakraborty and M. S. Chhetri, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2008, 18, 201.
 17. B. Chakraborty, S. Kafley and M. S. Chhetri, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2010, 49, 102.
 18. B. Chakraborty, S. Kafley and M. S. Chhetri, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2008, 18, 203.
 19. B. Chakraborty, M. S. Chhetri and A. Samanta, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2010 (in press).
 20. B. Chakraborty and M. S. Chhetri, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2008, 17, 213.